

Tracking the increase of the share of G7
ODA employment and skills promotion
programmes
directed specifically towards green sectors
and greening traditional sectors

Concept note

Note: the analysis presented in this paper is based on research work (data analysis and expert interviews), which was still ongoing at the time of drafting this version of the paper. Therefore, the final version of the analysis may require certain amendments or adjustments.

Mantas Sekmokas, Independent Expert
on behalf of Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ)

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	1
1. Introduction.....	2
2. Operationalising the indicator	4
2.1 Input-type indicators for steering ODA programming.....	4
2.2 Operationalising G7 commitment as an input-type indicator	5
2.3 Defining the scope of the indicator	6
3. The keyword approach for defining the scope	7
4. The CRS activity purpose codes approach for defining the scope.....	8
4.1 Employment Promotion programmes	8
4.1.1 Review of policy/guidance documents	9
4.1.2 Country- and institution-specific assessment	10
4.1.3 SDG-8 marker in OECD DAC statistics	11
4.2 Skills promotion programmes	12
5. Defining the “greening” aspect of relevant ODA activities: DAC policy marker system .	13
6. Discussion	14
6.1 The scope of ODA employment promotion programmes	14
6.2 The scope of ODA skills promotion programmes	14
6.3 The “greening” aspect of ODA activities	15
7. Implementation scenarios.....	16
8. Next steps.....	18
References.....	19
Annex I. The original list of CRS purpose codes	20

Executive Summary

On 28 June 2022, the G7 leaders committed to increase the share of official development assistance programmes, aimed at skills and employment promotion, which are directed specifically towards green sectors or greening of traditional sectors, in alignment with their emerging and developing partner countries' strategies, and subject to budgetary processes. To enable the **tracking of the commitment**, it needs to be operationalized as a statistical indicator. This paper presents a detailed analysis of the feasibility and the possible **approaches of using OECD DAC statistics** for tracking the commitment. The analysis was based on a review of relevant policy documentation, interviews with experts from the G7 countries and key multilateral organisations as well as the analysis of available OECD ODA statistics.

Following the commitment by the G7 Leaders, **Germany proposed two possible approaches** for identifying the relevant dimensions and tracking the commitment. The two proposals included (i) a **“keyword”** approach and (ii) an approach based on **CRS purpose codes and DAC policy makers**. Given that the “keyword” approach may take some time until it is implemented, the second proposal can be used as an initial solution, exploiting readily available data from the OECD DAC statistics. Nevertheless, the **two solutions are complementary** and elements from both solutions will likely be needed for tracking the G7 commitment.

The **operationalization of the indicator** requires a statistical definition of each of the key dimensions of the commitment, defining, in statistical terms, the coverage of “skills promotion programmes”, “employment promotion programmes” as well as the “green” targeting of those programmes. The analysis, presented in the paper, suggests:

- In terms of defining the scope of **“employment promotion” programmes**, a rather **broad understanding** of such programmes across G7 countries and multilateral institutions could be used. They usually include activities targeted at **employment creation and broader employment policies**. However, they also frequently include the various activities focused on **private sector development**, providing support for financial and business services, industry, trade and tourism;
- In terms of defining the scope of **“skills promotion” programmes**, there may be rationale to include all types of education and training programmes;
- In terms of defining the **“green” targeting** of relevant programmes, the OECD DAC policy marker system can be used. The analysis in the paper suggests, that for tracking the commitment, activities considered relevant in terms of “green” targeting should include activities receiving **any of the two scores** (score “1” or score “2”), for at least **one of the five “green” policy markers**.

The paper also presents a number of more detailed implementation scenarios for tracking the commitment. It highlights the ease of implementing tracking using CRS purpose codes and “green” markers, but also recognizing the added value of tracking based on “keyword” approach, in particular if linked to the presence of relevant results indicators, which could help link the tracking of inputs to the monitoring and evaluation of the results of investment.

1. Introduction

This paper presents further analysis of the feasibility and possible approaches of using OECD DAC statistics for tracking the commitment, adopted by the leaders of G7 countries, stating:

*“By 2025, we **will increase the share of our ODA employment and skills promotion programmes** that is directed specifically towards **green sectors and greening traditional sectors**, in alignment with our emerging and developing partner countries’ strategies and subject to our budgetary processes.”*

[G7 Leaders’ Communiqué](#), Elmau, 28 June 2022

Following the proclamation of the commitment by the G7 Leaders, Germany proposed two possible approaches on how to track the increase of the share of ODA employment and skills promotion programmes directed towards ‘green’. Both of these approaches, designed in consultation with the OECD and G7 experts, are based on Official Development Assistance (ODA) statistics, compiled via the OECD Development Assistance Committee (DAC) Creditor Reporting System (CRS). These approaches include:

- i. Tracking the commitment by introducing a new keyword, allowing to directly identify ODA activities, falling under the commitment (this option was proposed following a recommendation by the OECD).
- ii. Tracking the commitment by identifying those sectors (via CRS purpose codes¹) best representing ‘employment and skills promotion programmes’. The share of green investment in those sectors would then be measured with the help of “green” DAC policy markers. These markers indicate, if the policy objectives of an ODA activity target any of the four objectives of the Rio Convention on [biodiversity](#), [climate change \(adaptation and/or mitigation\)](#) and [desertification](#)², or a fifth, more general [aid to environment](#) objective.

It is likely, as will be detailed further in the paper, that the two approaches are not mutually exclusive. Notably, for being able to track the commitment, the keyword approach may require a combination either with the CRS purpose codes and/or with the “green” policy markers to enable the calculation of the share of “green” among all of the ODA employment and skills promotion programmes. Alternatively, more than one keyword may be required if tracking is to be carried out without using the CRS purpose codes or the policy markers.

¹ <https://www.oecd.org/dac/financing-sustainable-development/development-finance-standards/purposecodessectorclassification.htm>

² https://www.oecd.org/dac/environment-development/Revised%20climate%20marker%20handbook_FINAL.pdf

The analysis in this paper builds upon the original proposals by the Germany G7 presidency, including the proposal submitted to the OECD WP-Stat meeting on 29 September 2020 on the implementation of the key word approach. It also includes the review of relevant policy documentation, the OECD DAC statistical data as well as interviews with experts from the G7 countries and key multilateral organisations (the ILO, the OECD and the European Commission), engaged in ODA for employment and skills promotion. The review was carried out by an independent expert, engaged by the GIZ, over the months of October and November, 2022. The remainder of the paper provides a more detailed analysis of the possibilities and challenges as well as assess the key options, available for operationalising the G7 commitment as a concrete statistical indicator, which can be used for tracking the commitment.

The paper is structured in the following way. Section 2 proposed a general approach for the operationalising the G7 commitment as an input-type indicator. It includes an overview of the type of indicators used for programming and evaluation of ODA activities, with a particular focus on input-type indicators; provides the requirements for operationalising the G7 commitment as an input-type indicator to support ODA programming; identifies the key dimensions which need to be defined in statistical terms and discuss the central challenge for operationalising the commitment – defining the operational scope of “ODA employment and skills promotion programmes”.

Section 3 discusses the proposal for introducing a new criterion in the OECD DAC data collection, notably a dedicated “keyword” to identify relevant activities in OECD DAC statistics and use it for compiling the indicator required for tracking the commitment.

Section 4 describes the alternative approach for defining the scope of the possible indicator for tracing, using criteria/categories, already available in OECD DAC statistics, which can be used for defining the “skills” and “employment promotion” dimensions of the indicator.

Sections 5 provide the analysis of possible approaches as well as existing OECD DAC statistical data for defining the targeting of relevant ODA programmes towards “greening”.

Section 6 discusses the implications of the analysis and provide pointers towards most promising definitions of each of the three key dimensions for compiling the indicator to track G7 commitment.

Section 7 presents a number of scenarios for compiling the necessary indicator and initiating process of tracking the G7 commitment and provides a preliminary assessment of the benefits and drawbacks for each of the scenario. The section concludes with an initial recommendation as regards the most promising scenarios to be selected for implementation.

Finally, section 8 introduces a proposal for the next steps towards tracking the commitment.

2. Operationalising the indicator

2.1 Input-type indicators for steering ODA programming

Development cooperation is always carried out with an intention to achieve certain policy and developmental objectives. To ensure, that programming and implementation of ODA activities follows these objectives and is effective in delivering them, ODA donors and multilateral organizations use a variety of indicators to help them steer programming and assessing the impact of investment. In many cases, such indicators are organized within broader indicator frameworks, usually following a standard input-output approach (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. A generic input-output framework for steering ODA investment programmes. Source: OECD, 2013.

The proclaimed **commitment by G7** to increase the share of ODA employment and skills promotion programmes directed specifically towards green sectors and greening of traditional sectors, is clearly an **input-type indicator**, intended to help steering ODA programming and intervention design. This G7 commitment can also be related to several input-type indicators, already used by individual ODA donors and related to skills and/or employment domain. For example, the latest iteration of the results framework (Global Europe Results Framework – GERF³), used by the European Commission to collect and measure key results of EU international cooperation programmes, include three input-type indicators, assigned towards implementing SDG-8 and thus potentially related to employment promotion:

- GERF 3.3 Amount and share of EU-funded external assistance contributing to strengthening investment climate
- GERF 3.4 Amount and share of EU-funded external assistance contributing to: (a) aid for trade, (b) aid for trade to LDCs, and (c) trade facilitation
- GERF 3.5 Leverage of EU blending and guarantee operations financed by EU external assistance, measured as: (a) Investment leverage ratio, (b) Total eligible financial institution financing leverage ratio, (c) Private financing leverage ratio.

³ <https://europa.eu/capacity4dev/eu-rfi>

2.2 Operationalising G7 commitment as an input-type indicator

To enable tracking of the G7 commitment, it has to be operationalized as a statistical indicator. Notably, this means that all relevant dimensions from the commitment need to be identified and their operational definition in statistical terms needs to be elaborated. A verbatim partitioning of the G7 commitment indicates four dimensions defining the indicator scope:

- ODA employment promotion programmes;
- ODA skills promotion programmes;
- Relevant ODA programmes directed specifically at green sectors;
- Relevant ODA programmes directed specifically at greening of traditional sectors.

The first two dimensions define the type of programmes addressed in the commitment, i.e. the programmes having as their intended objective the {development} of skills and the promotion of employment. These two dimensions would help to define the denominator of the required indicator. The third dimension indicates the type of economic sectors, towards which the above-mentioned programmes should be directed, while the fourth dimension indicates both a type of economic sectors (i.e., “traditional”), towards which the programmes should be directed as well as the kind of effect they should have (i.e., “greening”). These two latter dimensions would then help to define the numerator of the indicator. In summary, the required indicator can be framed in the following way:

$$\frac{\text{The volume of "green" ODA for employment and skills}}{\text{The "total" volume of ODA for employment and skills}} = \text{share of "green" (\%)}$$

The operationalization of the indicator further requires a statistical definition of each of these four dimensions. The proposed data source, intended to be used for feeding the data for the indicator, is the OECD DAC statistics on ODA. These statistics measure the flows of official development assistance to the ODA recipients, as indicated on the DAC list of countries and territories as well as multilateral development institutions and is measured on a grant-equivalent basis. More detailed definitions are available on the dedicated OECD website⁴. The data source, selected for tracking the commitment, in addition has the following implications:

- Defining the applicable list of ODA donors. These are assumed to be all the G7 countries as well as the EU, as being parties to the communiqué;
- The need to define the applicable list of ODA recipients. These are assumed to be all the eligible countries and territories on the DAC list;
- The need to identify the sector of ODA. This implies, that only sector-allocable ODA can be used for tracking and ODA activities which are not sector allocable as well as aid via multilateral bodies⁵, cannot be used for tracking.

⁴ <https://www.oecd.org/dac/financing-sustainable-development/development-finance-standards/officialdevelopmentassistancedefinitionandcoverage.htm>

⁵ <https://www.oecd.org/dac/financing-sustainable-development/development-finance-standards/oecdmethodologyforcalculatingimputedmultilateraloda.htm>

2.3 Defining the scope of the indicator

As noted in the previous section, the G7 commitment includes four key dimensions, which need to be operationalized (defined) in statistical terms for the compilation of the indicator. These four dimensions use three main concepts in terms of their definition: the purpose of the programme (e.g. skills or employment promotion), economic sector, to which the programme is targeted (e.g. green sectors and traditional sectors) and the type of effect expected (greening – as relevant for the traditional sectors).

From the perspective of OECD DAC statistics, it includes multiple categories for identifying ODA activities, relevant for the G7 commitment. Notably, OECD DAC statistical database includes the detailed list of all relevant ODA activities, as reported by ODA donors. For each of these activities, the data set includes such categories as the socio-economic area, which the activities intend to foster (i.e., the so-called CRS purpose codes). Each activity is also assessed in terms of policy markers – indicating if the activity was designed with the aim of achieving a certain policy objective (such as the four Rio markers, representing policy objectives of the Rio Convention). Furthermore, for each of the ODA activity it can be indicated if it contributes to the implementation of one or several of the sustainable development goals (SDGs). Finally, each activity, as reported to the OECD, also include a short textual description of the activity, which could be used to identify the purpose and/or scope of the activity.

In addition, from the perspective of the statistical datasets held by the donors, further two avenues could potentially be used to identify relevant activities. If the donor in a systematic way records, or can otherwise easily extract the objectives of all (or most) of the ODA activities, such data could be used to identify activities, relevant for the G7 commitment. Finally, if the donor in a systematic way records, or can otherwise easily extract the indicators measuring the expected results, outcomes or impacts of the ODA activities, these again can be used to identify activities relevant for the ODA commitment.

Systematic recording of either the objectives and/or the results/outcomes/impact indicators in the national statistical or administrative datasets should be carried out in such a fashion, so as to enable easy selection and extraction of activities with relevant objectives or indicators. This implies, that objectives and/or indicators would need to be recorded in the datasets in a digital format, have dedicated field(s) for their recording as well as the way for filling-in such fields should be relatively standardized.

The approach, which would facilitate the use of such data the most, is when there exists a standard list of objectives and/or indicators. In such a case, a selection of objectives/indicators covering e.g., employment and skills promotion could be done relatively quickly. Subsequently, the relevant data for the ODA activities, which include such objectives and/or indicators, could be easily extracted. From the interviews, it has been understood, that at least in some countries and multilateral institutions, such systems already exist or are being implemented. However, it also seems, that such systems are likely to be available only in part of the G7 countries.

3. The keyword approach for defining the scope

Identifying ODA activities which have a direct/explicit relation to skills and/or employment promotion, is where a dedicated keyword could be particularly useful. If the countries can in a feasible way (via objectives, indicators or otherwise) identify the ODA activities relevant for the G7 commitment, these could be indicated by the dedicated keyword and included in the common OECD DAC data collection. Nevertheless, the operational definition of the keyword would also need to be agreed among respective donors, to ensure consistency and comparability of data.

Notably, the definition of the keyword would need to cover some or all four dimensions of the G7 commitment as detailed before. Furthermore, a single keyword on its own would not be sufficient for compiling the required indicator. For example, if the keyword would include all the four dimensions as detailed above, it would only provide data for the numerator of the indicator (e.g., the volume of green ODA for skills and employment promotion), while calculating the denominator of the indicator would require a different category, identifying employment and skills promotion programmes, irrespective of their “green” focus. Therefore, either a minimum of two keywords, or a combination of a keyword and other criteria (e.g. green markers, SDG markers and/or CRS codes) would be needed to compile the indicator.

The distinct advantage of the keyword method is the robustness of data that it will produce, as well as a greater efficiency in assessing the data. However, the introduction of the keyword in national data and reporting systems will take some time, depending on the characteristics of the respective systems. Therefore, it is assumed that the method cannot be used immediately for tracking the G7 ‘green jobs and skills’ commitment as of 2022. For the keyword to be implemented, the G7 will have to agree on one keyword including green jobs and green skills. The keyword needs to be backed up with a clear and comprehensive definition.

A proposal to include the key word approach into G7 members and OECD members reporting was already proposed by GER at the WP-Stat meeting on 29th September 2022, based on a respective room-document. The proposal recognized, that the introduction of the keyword in national data and reporting systems is likely to take some time, depending on the characteristics of the respective systems. Therefore, it is assumed that the method cannot be used immediately for tracking the G7 ‘green jobs and skills’ commitment as of 2022. Nevertheless, to facilitate the implementation of the keyword, the WP-STAT could be requested adding it to the list of keywords included in Annex 13 of the Statistical Directives.

4. The CRS activity purpose codes approach for defining the scope

4.1 Employment Promotion programmes

Providing an operational definition of what kind of ODA activities are to be considered as employment promotion programmes is arguably the most challenging part of tracking the G7 commitment. This is due to the very broad, cross-disciplinary nature of employment promotion, as has been already recognised in the original proposal developed by the German G7 presidency. In addition, there does not seem to exist a commonly accepted practice at the international level of which types of actions/activities would be considered as promoting employment. One can think of at least six ways how to identify, which ODA activities are to be considered as employment promotion programmes:

1. On the basis of existing policy/guidance documents, which define the scope of employment promotion. This seems to have been the basis for the original proposal by the German G7 presidency, following its employment-oriented economic policy framework, used for steering the design of employment-relevant development cooperation projects. Despite their scarcity, the analysis in this paper presents several such descriptions, identified via a rapid literature review;
2. On the basis of country- or institution-specific assessment of what is inferred to constitute employment promotion activities in development cooperation policy context of that particular country and/or institution. The analysis in this paper is informed by a number of interviews with experts from G7 countries as well as the key multilateral institutions engaged, through development cooperation, in employment promotion (notably the ILO, the OECD and the European Commission);
3. On the basis of identifying which specific activities or which activity sectors are being assigned as contributing to the SDG 8 – which is the main SDG objective dedicated to cover employment promotion. The analysis in this paper presents the findings of exactly this analysis, using the OECD DAC statistical data;
4. On the basis of analyzing textual descriptions of ODA activities, in particular those included in OECD DAC data collection.
5. On the basis of identifying ODA activities which were designed with having employment promotion as one of their objectives. This data is not explicitly available from the OECD DAC statistics, but it may be available within statistical or administrative data systems of individual donors. For example, this seems to be the case for ODA programmes, implemented by the ILO and the European Commission.
6. On the basis of identifying ODA activities, which, as part of their programming logic, includes employment-relevant output or outcomes indicators. This data is not explicitly available from the OECD DAC statistics, but it may be available within statistical or administrative data systems of individual donors. For example, this seems to be the case for ODA programmes, implemented by the European Commission

The first three of the approaches will be the focus of subsequent analysis, with a particular focus on OECD DAC statistics, given the efficiency of using comparable statistical data.

4.1.1 Review of policy/guidance documents

Arguably, the most relevant policy framework which can be used to infer the scope of employment promotion policy is the Sustainable Development Goals framework and in particular the SDG 8: “promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all”. SDG 8 includes twelve targets, covering such topics as sustainable economic growth; productivity; job creation and enterprise growth; improving resource efficiency; full employment and decent work with equal pay; youth employment, education and training; ending of modern slavery, trafficking and child labour; labour rights; sustainable tourism; universal access to banking; aid for trade; development of global youth employment strategy.

In addition, at least three other existing frameworks have been identified, which broadly define the scope of employment promotion programmes. These include the BMZ, GIZ and KfW employment-oriented economic policy framework (see Figure 2 below), the “integrated approach” by the ILO towards employment promotion/national employment policy⁶ and the European Commission manual on promoting employment and decent work in development cooperation. All the frameworks point towards rather broad understanding of employment promotion, often comprising both the supply and demand sides of employment creation. The most comprehensive list of policies, which are relevant for employment promotion, is available in the European Commission manual, represented in Figure 3 below.

Figure 2. Employment-oriented Economic Policy Framework. Background note for the Development Track: Just Transition through Green Jobs and Skills Promotion, German G7 Presidency, 2022.

⁶ <https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/employment-promotion/lang--en/index.htm>

Figure 3. Policies, relevant for employment promotion. European Commission, 2018, p. 66.

The original proposal by the German G7 presidency focused primarily on the areas skills development and private sector development (including financial services, trade and tourism). The full list of areas in the original proposal and defined by CRS purpose codes, is provided in the Annex I.

4.1.2 Country- and institution-specific assessment

Expert interviews point towards uncertainty as to which of the demand-sided areas of employment promotion would be most relevant to be included for G7 commitment tracking. In particular, uncertainty was indicated as regards the relevance of including infrastructure-related sectors, industry-specific ODA and more generally uncertainty as to which part of private sector development activities should be considered as relevant for employment promotion. [Text possibly to be amended based on further analysis and interviews]

4.1.3 SDG-8 marker in OECD DAC statistics

The OECD DAC statistical dataset includes a dedicated data-field (marker) which can be used to indicate, to which of the SDG(s) the development cooperation activities intend to contribute. Unfortunately, the scope and the level of detail of SDG focus of aid reporting in OECD DAC statistics is uneven across donors. Nevertheless, analysis of SDG focus of aid activities by CRS activity purpose code was possible for four of G7 countries, using the latest available data covering the reference year 2020.

The analysis was carried out in the subsequent fashion: all the ODA activities for the year 2020, for each specific G7 member country, were downloaded from the OECD DAC database. Furthermore, an additional indicator was created, identifying if SDG 8 goal is included among the SDG goals, reported in the dedicated “SDG Focus” column of the dataset for each ODA activity. Furthermore, data aggregation procedure was carried out to calculate the number of ODA activities belonging to the same CRS purpose code and calculating the share of activities, belonging to that CRS purpose code, which include SDG 8 focus, out of all activities, belonging to that CRS purpose code. The summary of the results is provided in Table 1.

Table 1. The share of ODA activities, indicated to have SDG 8 as their focus, 2020

	Canada	France [^]	Italy	Japan	Average [†]
Employment creation	100%	59%	63%	74%	74%
Other employment policies[‡]	10%	1%	19%	33%	16%
Transport	53%	0%	14%	23%	23%
Energy	28%	3%	15%	16%	16%
Financial services	75%	83%	43%	94%	74%
Business services	47%	31%	66%	95%	60%
Agriculture, forestry, fishing	58%	6%	19%	2%	21%
Industry, mining, construction[*]	74%	1%	47%	51%	43%
Trade policies	23%	7%	66%	90%	47%
Tourism	96%	29%	71%	91%	72%

Notes: sector-specific training activities are excluded from these calculations. [^]For France, the shares of activities with SDG-8 focus is generally lower compared to other countries as a significant proportion of ODA activities do not have any SDG indicated as their focus. [†]Unweighted average. [‡]It should be noted, that other employment-related policies, such as social protection, are often indicated to focus on other, more relevant SDGs, such as SDG 1 (which has a target on social protection) or SDG 10 (which focus on inequality). ^{*}Construction sector primarily includes generic construction policy, as, according to OECD DAC methodology, sector-specific construction activities should be reported under each individual sector.

4.2 Skills promotion programmes

Broadly speaking, purposeful skills development may include all the activities with the aim to develop a person’s skills set as well as their social context – be it in an educational institution, workplace or during free time. However, for the purpose of the G7 commitment, the reference to specific economic sectors suggests that the scope of ambition primarily focuses on labour market relevant skills. OECD DAC statistical data, with the help of CRS activity purpose codes, allows to identify ODA directed towards education and training, identifying in total 15 education sector codes at the most detailed level, as well as designated codes for training, focused on particular economic activity sectors.

In countries at a high level of economic development, the systems most frequently associated with the development of labour market relevant skills are initial and continuing vocational education and training. Also, higher education is likewise frequently perceived to provide labour market relevant skills. This is assumed to have been the basis for the original proposal by the German G7 presidency, considering that skills promotion programmes could be defined as including upper-secondary education and training, higher education, advanced technical and managerial training, sector-specific training as well as education not defined by level.

Nevertheless, using OECD DAC statistical data, three different interpretations of G7 commitment as concerns the “skills” dimension could be implemented in practice:

- A narrow definition, only including specific training for “green” and “traditional” sectors, if G7 commitment wording would be interpreted in verbatim;
- An intermediate definition, adding pre-labour market entry educational programmes (e.g., vocational training, higher education and advanced technical training) to the activities included in the narrow definition);
- A broad definition, including all education and training activities identifiable via CRS activity purpose codes.

To further inform the reflection and an analysis of SDG-8 attribution to ODA activities, related to education and training could be carried out using latest OECD DAC statistical data, in a similar way as done for defining employment promotion.

Table 2. The share of ODA training activities, indicated to have SDG 8 as their focus, 2020

	Canada	France [^]	Italy	Japan	Average [†]
Education, level unspecified	3%	1%	3%	3%	3%
Basic education, incl. for adults	7%	2%	15%	78%	26%
Upper-secondary education, excl. VET	8%	1%	15%	7%	8%
Vocational training	22%	13%	23%	75%	33%
Higher education	7%	3%	4%	75%	22%
Advanced technical training	39%	27%	19%	0%	21%
Sector-specific training	30%	5%	38%	8%	20%

Notes: [^]For France, the shares of activities with SDG-8 focus is generally lower compared to other countries as a significant proportion of ODA activities do not have any SDG indicated as their focus. [†]Unweighted average.

5. Defining the “greening” aspect of relevant ODA activities: DAC policy marker system

The “green” focus of ODA activities can be identified using the DAC policy marker system, which indicate activities, targeted to a particular policy objective. Among the 12 policy markers used in OECD DAC statistics, there are five policy markers which related to “green” policy objectives: Biodiversity; Climate change mitigation; Climate change adaptation; Desertification and Aid to environment.

Following the methodological guidance for compiling OECD DAC statistics, each ODA activity should be screened if the activity targets a particular policy objective. If such targeting is identified, then a score is assigned to the activity depending how important the policy objective is in the design and impact of the activity. The scoring systems is as follows:

- The policy objective, defined by the marker, is a principal objective for the activity, explicitly stated in the objectives of the activity and being fundamental in its design and implementation. In such a case a score of “2” is assigned to that particular ODA activity in reference to the specific policy marker.
- The policy objective, defined by the marker, is a significant, but secondary objective for the activity and while being important, is not one of the principal reasons for undertaking the activity. In such case a score of 1” is assigned to that particular ODA activity in reference to the specific policy marker.
- A score of “0” is assigned if the ODA activity is not targeted to the policy objective.

Table 3. The share of ODA activities with green markers’ scores, 2020

	Employment-related		Skills-related		Total	
	1 or 2	Only 2	1 or 2	Only 2	1 or 2	Only 2
Canada	46%	17%	36%	15%	42%	16%
France	10%	3%	6%	1%	7%	2%
Germany	34%	11%	5%	1%	12%	3%
Italy	36%	10%	15%	5%	19%	6%
Japan	4%	1%	12%	0%	7%	1%
United Kingdom	32%	10%	14%	3%	25%	7%
United States	28%	10%	21%	12%	24%	11%
G7 average†	27%	9%	16%	5%	20%	7%

Notes: †Unweighted average. The basis of the calculation is the number of activities with/without green markers score, but not their monetary volume. “1 or 2” indicates the share of activities, which have a score of at least 1 for at least 1 of the 5 green markers. “2” indicates the share of activities, with have a score of at least 2 for at least 1 of the 5 green markers. Employment-related activities include employment creation, other employment policies, financial services, business services, industry, mining, construction, trade policies and tourism activities. Skills-related activities include the whole education sector.

6. Discussion

Based on the analysis presented above, several observations can be made as regards the definition of the scope of individual dimensions of the indicator.

6.1 The scope of ODA employment promotion programmes

The analysis presented in section 5 suggests, that, in general, employment promotion both from policy as well as from practical reporting in the OECD DAC is understood to be rather broad, including, in particular, the different activities contributing to private sector development, including financial services, business services, industrial development, trade and tourism. Activity sectors, which seem to be less directly related to employment promotion are agriculture (incl. forestry and fishing), transport and energy. Also, other employment policies (i.e., social protection, statistical capacity development, labour rights or social dialogue) are less frequently indicated as related to SDG-8. However, these policies may be more directly related to other SDGs and thus being reported as focused towards implementing them, rather than SDG-8.

Based on this analysis, the areas of ODA activity, **most frequently associated** to SDG-8, would include:

- Employment creation (CRS purpose code 16020)
- Financial services (CRS purpose code 240)
- Business services (CRS purpose code 250)
- Tourism (CRS purpose code 332)

Areas of ODA activity, **moderately frequently associated** to SDG-8, would include:

- Industry, mining and construction (CRS purpose code 320)
- Trade policies (CRS purpose code 331)

The area of ODA activity, **related more to the quality of employment** rather than employment promotion per-se and as such more linked to other SDGs, than SDG-8, includes:

- Other employment-related policies (CRS purpose codes 16010, 16062, 16070, 16080)

6.2 The scope of ODA skills promotion programmes

The analysis presented in section 4 suggests, that, as currently reported in the OECD DAC dataset, none of the education sector seems to particularly strongly linked to SDG-8 and thus inferred to be labour-market related. Nevertheless, there is certain ranking between education sub-sectors, with education not defined by level and general upper-secondary education less frequently associated to SDG-8 than the other education sub-sectors.

Overall, there could be rationale **to include all education sectors** for the monitoring of G7 commitment based on these arguments:

- The importance of both basic as well as advanced skills for the labour market, also testified by the presence of basic skills programmes for adults;

- A relatively large share of young persons in countries receiving ODA leave education before reaching upper-secondary level of education, especially in least developed economies;
- Relatively low differences in terms of SDG-8 orientation between different sub-sectors of education are observed based on existing OECD DAC data;
- The importance of promoting “green” attitudes throughout all education stages;
- Ease of data processing, analysis and communication, when selecting aggregated categories to be included for tracking.

6.3 The “greening” aspect of ODA activities

The OECD DAC policy marker system allows identified ODA activities whose objectives correspond to the policy objectives defined by the selected marker(s). This most clearly relates to the part of the G7 commitment defining the focus of skills and employment promotion programmes towards “greening of traditional sectors”. However, policy markers define the objectives of ODA activities somewhat more broadly, without reference to any particular sector(s), towards which the greening effort is targeted at.

A key technical decision for tracking the G7 commitment, using the policy marker system, is to decide which score level is satisfactory for an activity to be considered sufficiently contributing to the “greening” effort. As presented in section 7, on average only 7% of relevant G7 ODA activities have “greening” effort as their principal objective, as defined by DAC policy markers. Another 13% have such an objective as significant, but not principal in the design or implementation of ODA activities. Thus, on average, across the G7 countries the share of ODA activities scoring either 1 or 2 on any of the 5 “green” policy markers is 20%.

The choice between broader or narrower definition of “green” effort is, primarily, a tradeoff between quality and quantity. Notably, if the more selective definition is chosen, it is expected that an effort will be directed towards smaller number, but more targeted ODA activities, each of them individually likely having stronger contribution towards greening of the economies. On the other hand, a broader definition would likely allow to embed the greening effort in a broader range of projects. In addition, some of the interviewees pointed out, that usually in their context ODA activities are expected to have only one primary objective. Thus, in case employment or skills promotion is the primary objective, in most instances the “green” objective would be considered only as secondary.

Therefore, recognizing that both types of activities may be important in contributing to the greening effort, but that score 2 is likely to be the score assigned most frequently, tracking could be carried out taking into account both scores, i.e., assessing both the overall share of ODA activities receiving a non-zero green marker score, but also the proportion of high-impact projects (i.e., those receiving a score of 2).

7. Implementation scenarios

Based on the analysis presented above, for initiating actual tracking of G7 commitment, the following implementation scenarios could be envisaged:

Scenario 1: tracking the commitment via the combination of CRS purpose codes and green markers.

- **Benefits:** a ready-made solution without any additional effort required to compile the data; historic time-series available; clear and consistent identification of sectors across countries due to well-established methodology; relatively easier to analyze and communicate.
- **Drawbacks:** some uncertainty, if all the ODA activities included for tracking would have explicit employment-related objectives or result indicators. *However, the sectors proposed to include generally have moderate to high SDG-8 link across the analyzed G7 countries; all the selected sectors are included in existing policy definitions/frameworks referring to employment promotion.*

Scenario 2: tracking the commitment via the combination of SDG-8 marker (for employment promotion), CRS purpose codes (for skills promotion) and green markers.

- **Benefits:** more precise identification of ODA activities, which aims to contribute to the implementation of SDG-8 and thus can be inferred to have a logical link to employment promotion concept; follows an existing methodology and has a clear link to existing policy framework.
- **Drawbacks:** additional effort required by some G7 countries, where SDG markers are being reported to the OECD less regularly; this approach also may reveal different practices across countries in attributing the SDG markers; furthermore, the values of the denominator of the indicator may fluctuate more significantly from year to year depending on how many projects are found to be relevant for SDG-8.

The following scenarios describe how tracking could be pursued by introducing of a new keyword in OECD DAC data collection. In this case, multiple sub-scenarios are available.

Scenario 3a: using the keyword to identify ODA activities focused on employment promotion, using CRS purpose codes for defining skills promotion and green markers for defining “green” orientation of investment.

- **Benefits:** the keyword only covers a single dimension, thus easier to implement than multi-dimensional keywords and focuses on the dimension where current OECD DAC data is least specific.
- **Drawbacks:** requires developing a definition and methodology of identifying activities corresponding to the keyword as well as adjustments in the data collection process at country level.

- **Further options** how the keyword could define relevant ODA activities:
 - It could define ODA activities in a similar, but in a more focused sense as compared to SDG-8 definition. This, however, seems to add little value over using an existing approach of reporting SDG-8.
 - It could define ODA activities based on criteria that ODA activity should have employment promotion as one of its main explicit objectives. This would be easier in those countries/institutions where exist systematic collection of data on the intervention logic and the objectives of ODA activities
 - It could define ODA activities based on criteria that ODA activity should have employment outcomes as one of its results indicators. This would be easier in those countries/institutions where exist systematic collection of data on the intervention logic and the results indicators of ODA activities. **A particular added-value** of such implementation modality would be the possible linkage to monitoring and evaluation (M&E) of the impact of G7 commitment, even possibly aggregating the impact across activities/institutions/countries.

Scenario 3b: using the keyword to identify ODA activities covering both employment and skills promotion dimensions, while using green markers for defining “green” orientation of investment.

- **Benefits:** having such a single criterion, would allow easy extraction of the data required for compiling the denominator of the indicator
- **Drawbacks:** requires developing a definition and methodology of identifying activities corresponding to the keyword but, compared to scenario 3a, now covering two dimensions (employment promotion and skills promotion) as well as adjustments in the data collection process at country level.
- **Further options** include, similarly as in scenario 3a, different approaches for defining if ODA activities have employment promotion and/or skills promotion as intention, objective and/or result indicator(s).

Scenario 3c: using the keyword to identify the “green” dimension of relevant ODA activities, while using CRS purpose codes to define employment promotion and skills promotion activities.

- **Benefits:** having a single code to identify if activity has a “green” orientation
- **Drawbacks:** little added value over existing criteria (green markers) while requiring development of a definition and methodology for a new marker as well as adjustments in the data collection process at country level.

Scenario 3d: using two separate keywords, one for defining the denominator of the indicator (i.e., employment promotion and skills promotion activities) and one for defining the numerator of the indicator, i.e., the “green” dimension of investment.

- **Benefits:** having two single markers makes very easy to extract and process the data for users
- **Drawbacks:** combination of drawbacks as in scenarios 3b and 3c

Summary assessment: in terms of ease of implementation and smallest drawbacks, **Scenario 1** would seem to be most attractive. On the other hand, in terms of highest added-value, **Scenario 3a** with the option of focusing the keyword to capture presence of employment-related results indicators, would seem to be most attractive and bring the biggest added-value tracking, as well as monitoring and evaluation efforts. However, the time required to deploy Scenario 3a is uncertain and it may not be available for tracking the commitment over the short or even medium-term.

8. Next steps

Following from the analysis presented in this paper, it is therefore proposed:

- **Over the short-term**, for pragmatic reasons, to use the method of combining CRS purpose codes and green markers as the initial solution for tracking increases in the share of G7 'green jobs and skills' ODA commitments.
- **Overt the medium-term**, to start the work on introducing the new keyword tracking method, simultaneously to the refinement of the CRS code/marker combination method.

References

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Annex I. The original list of CRS purpose codes

DAC-Codes Vocational Education, Higher Education & Employment	
DAC5-Code/ FBS	Description
110	Education
111	Education, Level Unspecified
11110	Education policy and administrative management
11120	Education facilities and training
11130	Teacher training
11182	Educational research
113	Secondary Education
11330	Vocational training
114	Post-Secondary Education
11420	Higher Education
11430	Advanced technical and managerial training
120	Health
121	Health, General
12181	Medical education/training
122	Basic Health
12281	Health personnel development
130	Population Policies/Programmes & Reproductive Health
13081	Personnel development for population and reproductive
160	Other Social Infrastructure & Services
16010	Social Protection
16020	Employment creation
16062	Statistical capacity building
16070	Labour rights
16080	Social dialogue
210	Transport & Storage
21081	Education and training in transport and storage
311	Agriculture
31181	Agricultural education/training
430	Other Multisector
43081	Multisector education/training
43082	Research/scientific institutions

DAC-Codes Financial System Development	
DAC5-Code/ FBS	Description
240	Banking & Financial Services
24010	Financial policy and administrative management
24020	Monetary institutions
24030	Formal sector financial intermediaries
24040	Informal/semi-formal financial intermediaries
24050	Remittance facilitation, promotion and optimisation
24081	Education/training in banking and financial services

DAC-Codes Promotion Of The Financial Sector & Economic Policy (incl. Trade)	
DAC5-Code/ FBS	Description
250	Business & Other Services
25010	Business policy and administration
25020	Privatisation
25030	Business development services
25040	Responsible business conduct
321	Industry
32110	Industrial policy and administrative management
32120	Industrial development
32130	Small and medium-sized enterprises (SME) development
32140	Cottage industries and handicraft
32161	Agro-industries
32162	Forest industries
32163	Textiles, leather and substitutes
32164	Chemicals
32165	Fertilizer plants
32166	Cement/lime/plaster
32167	Energy manufacturing (fossil fuels)
32168	Pharmaceutical production
32169	Basic metal industries
32170	Non-ferrous metal industries
32171	Engineering
32172	Transport equipment industry
32173	Modern biofuels manufacturing
32174	Clean cooking appliances manufacturing
32182	Technological research and development
322	Mineral Resources & Mining
32210	Mineral/mining policy and administrative management
32220	Mineral prospection and exploration
32261	Coal
32262	Oil and gas (upstream)
32263	Ferrous metals
32264	Nonferrous metals
32265	Precious metals/materials
32266	Industrial minerals
32267	Fertilizer minerals
32268	Offshore minerals
331	Trade Policies & Regulations
33110	Trade policy and administrative management
33120	Trade facilitation
33130	Regional trade agreements (RTAs)
33140	Multilateral trade negotiations
33150	Trade-related adjustment
33181	Trade education/training
332	Tourism
33210	Tourism policy and administrative management

